

METHODS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT LITERACY BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. *This article shows the importance of mastering the literacy of students based on an innovative approach. The reason, purpose and advantages of using the non-traditional method in the course of the lesson are analyzed.*

Keywords: *interactive method, "Blue pen" method, "Let's write by mistake" campaign, the method "Find the mistake", the method of "Working in small groups".*

Introduction. As a result of important socio-political events such as the independence of Uzbekistan and the legalization of Uzbek language as a state language, great changes are taking place in the attitude to education. For our independent republic, education of young people becomes even more important in a situation where the issue of training an entrepreneur and a creative, at the same time, literate person is important.

Granting the status of the state language to Uzbek language is a great event in the life of our country and nation. The dreams of our ancestors have come true. Thanks to the Law "On the State Language" and independence, the prestige of Uzbek language was restored, wide horizons were opened for its development. Our mother tongue is widely used in our republic not only as a communication tool, but also as a scientific, artistic and official language. Learning, reading and teaching the Uzbek language, publishing scientific and artistic works, educational literature in Uzbek language has been widely implemented. Our mother tongue has become one of the sacred symbols of our independent state, which stands among the flag, coat of arms, anthem, and Constitution, and is protected by law. However, there are issues that need to be implemented, defects that are being solved, and issues such as youth literacy, which are gaining urgency.

The current state of the education system is characterized by increasing role of non-traditional educational technologies. Learning by students with their help is much faster than with traditional technologies. These technologies will change the nature of knowledge development, acquisition and distribution, deepen and expand the content of the studied subjects, quickly update it, use more effective teaching methods, and also significantly expand the opportunity for education for everyone.

Today, in a number of developed countries, the methods that form the basis of great experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process are called interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most common and are widely used in all types of institutions. At the same time, there are many types of interactive educational methods, and there are suitable ones for the implementation of almost all tasks of the educational process. In practice, it is the teacher's skill to distinguish alternatives from them for specific purposes and use them in appropriate places.

Interactive methods that can be used to improve students' literacy are analyzed below.

From school days, other people like us start to evaluate us, they give us different grades, the most important thing is that if we have two mistakes in 100 words we write, that mistake is highlighted in red to show us that it is a bug. Notice that out of 100 words, only two are wrong,

but we're going to focus on those two. We don't pay much attention to 98 correctly spelled words, as a result, the child begins to suffer from perfectionism (achieving 100 percent results in everything), the fear of making mistakes appears in child's heart.

We are human, we have the right to make mistakes. The human mind gradually gets used to seeing such small mistakes.

What to do?

We should switch to the "**Blue pen**" method in schools, we should not highlight children's mistakes with a red pen, but comment on them with a blue pen, for example, "You write very well, if you practice writing even more, the mistakes will disappear."

We need to learn not to discourage the child by paying attention to mistakes, but to encourage him by giving him new strength.

I think that the "Blue pen" system should have been already used at schools, studying to the full "five" does not ensure a bright future for a child. We should teach the child not to be afraid of making mistakes, we should raise his good qualities to the highest and discuss his mistakes together, because the world is evil to those who seek vices, and the world is wisdom to those who seek wisdom.

In addition to this, it is also appropriate to implement the campaign "**We write without mistake**" to improve students' literacy. For this, at schools, all students are given words to write in a situation based on their age. Each student is given 10 words. The student who makes the fewest mistakes, i.e. the most number of correctly written words, becomes the winner of the campaign.

In order to achieve the correctness of written speech, compliance with the standards of literary language, to give an understanding of the tools that damage the correctness of speech, and to develop the competence of students to follow the standards of literary language in oral and written speech, the method "**Find the error**" is available.

In this process, the students are given the following tasks to identify the places where the spelling standards are not followed:

Fuqarolar yig'inlari faoliyatini samarali yo'lga qo'yishda jamoatchilik komissiyalarining o'rni sezilarli **bo'layapti**.

The role of public commissions in the effective implementation of the activities of citizens' gatherings is **becoming** significant.

"Barakalla, otao'g'il, bopladiniz!" O'g'li Hasanboyni bag'riga mahkam bosib, shunday deyishni diliga **tukkan** Ma'rufjon Hayitboyevni suhbatga tortamiz.

We will interview Marufjon Hayitbayev, who dreams of holding his son Hasanboy tightly in his arms and **saying** "Bless you, father's son!".

(Newspaper)

Solving: The first part of the sentence is written incorrectly. -yap form is added to the bases of verbs ending in a consonant, -ayap even if it is pronounced in case, written as -yap: bo'lyapti. Second sentence: The past tense form of -gan becomes -kan, -kan in pronunciation and spelling only when it is added to words ending with the adjective k, q, but because the root of the word button is the word "tug", it is written in the form of tuggan. The method "Find the error" can also be used to determine which words in the given sentences have damaged the accuracy of speech by using them incorrectly. Students' attention is drawn to the following examples:

1. New modern technology was installed at the enterprise.
2. New modern equipment was introduced to the enterprise.

Solving: an assignment is given to determine the dictionary meaning of the words technology and technique used in these sentences using the "Explanatory Dictionary of Uzbek Language".

Technology – about the production process, methods and tools, body of knowledge.

Equipment – working tools such as mechanisms and devices used in production.

These words are interchanged in pairs of sentences according to their usage and meaning. Using the word "technique" in sentence 1 and the word "equipment" in sentence 2, it is appropriate to formulate the sentence as follows:

1. New modern equipment was installed at the enterprise.
2. New modern technology was introduced to the enterprise.

At the same time, the exercises given in the textbook are directly aimed at increasing the student's literacy.

15.4-mashq. Quyidagi birliklarni "to'g'ri yozilgan" va "noto'g'ri yozilgan" kabi 2 ta guruhga bo'lib chiqing. "Noto'g'ri yozilgan" guruhiga kiritilgan birliklarni to'g'rilang va daftaringizga ko'chiring.

<u>muomala</u>	<u>bo'ysunish</u>	<u>mazxara</u>	passport	<u>metallar</u>
<u>dimog'li</u>	<u>mabodo</u>	<u>odamzot</u>	<u>ohangrabo</u>	<u>orzuqib</u>
<u>tarjimayi hol</u>	<u>chanqovbosti</u>	<u>nes-nobud bo'lmoq</u>		
<u>melodiy</u>	<u>mutloqo</u>	<u>naqarot</u>	<u>noshut</u>	<u>no'xat</u>
<u>daromat</u>	<u>davomat</u>	<u>poyafzal</u>	<u>boloxona</u>	<u>urushqoq</u>
<u>dapdurstdan</u>	<u>baynaminal</u>	<u>dasturilamal</u>		

It will be effective if the teacher of "Mother tongue" uses the interactive method "Working in small groups" when explaining the issues of national customs and rituals. Depending on the number of students, the class is divided into four or five groups. Each group is asked to find some type of customs and rituals and explain its significance. In this, the first group is tasked with defining the system of customs and ceremonies aimed at forming the upbringing of young people in the spirit of love for the Motherland. The second group is given the task of telling the customs and ceremonies that form the sense of civic duty and responsibility for the chosen profession in young people. The third group is told to explain customs and ceremonies aimed at improving the moral qualities of young people. The fourth group can be assigned to describe the system of educational activities that may become a tradition and ritual in the future.

After all the groups have made their presentations, the teacher summarizes and completes their thoughts. During the presentation period, students are allowed to react to the tasks given to them by other group members, give real examples, and critically analyze them. In order to avoid mutual disagreements in the groups, the teacher monitors and manages the process with vigilance and extreme vigilance, the answers of the groups are encouraged by the teacher. In the process of using this innovative educational technology, the students are interested in the traditions and rituals in life, as well as their importance in the education of a well-rounded person, as well as the answers of the fourth group.

Our experience shows that students include the following in the system of spiritual and educational activities, which may become traditions and rituals in the future:

They offer to hold the "Young Reader Conferences", "Young Reader" contests, "Excursion to historical places", festivals "My Loved Profession". In conclusion, today in educational institutions it is urgent to raise the education of the mother tongue to a new level - to the stage of systematic language learning, to develop orthographic and stylistic literacy in students, to form pragmatic competence in them, and on this basis to ensure speech and linguistic competence in oral and written forms.

We know that pedagogical software tools are designed for partial or complete automation of the learning process. They are considered one of the promising forms of increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, in which modern technologies are used as a teaching tool and come in handy in an innovative approach.

Since written works play an important role in the development of students' literacy, pedagogical software tools for organizing written works are used to create moving images related to the content of the text, to move the pictures in the text in harmony with sound, to vividly visualize, see, and hear the content of the text in the imagination of the students and mnemonic ability to develop harmoniously, increase students' activity, create a comfortable creative environment in the team, and arouse interest in the basics of science.

Recommendations

1. Texts on given speech topics, exercises, questions and tasks aimed at developing student's literacy, pictures and illustrations suitable for the content of speech topics should be connected with the grammatical topic.

2. It is necessary to give recommendations on the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, methods, exercises in the textbook, solutions to tasks and work on text and vocabulary in the process of teaching students about the subject of the mother tongue.

3. In order to improve students' literacy, it is necessary to pay attention to independent work, for this, it is necessary to prepare texts of spiritual and educational content and present them in the form of an audio speech.

4. The textbook of new generation must have control and measurement materials can be presented in the form of an electronic device as an appendix. In this case, each student will be able to determine the level of his knowledge and capabilities, self-examination, control and assessment of his educational potential in science.

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